

DECISION-MAKING MODEL FOR CONTROLLING A COLLABORATIVE ROBOT-MANIPULATOR BASED ON THE SENSOR FUSION METHOD AND THE RULES OF RULE-BASED SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents a combined decision-making model for controlling a collaborative robot-manipulator, which is based on the method of sensor data fusion (Sensor Fusion) and a system of rules (Rule-Based Systems). The proposed approach allows providing adaptive, reliable and interpretable control in the conditions of a dynamic production environment, typical for the concept of Industry 5.0. The modeling results confirm the effectiveness of the developed model and demonstrate its prospects for the further development of intelligent robotic systems.

Keywords: Collaborative Robot, Manipulator, Decision-Making, Sensor Fusion, Rule-Based Systems, Robotics, Industry 5.0, Data Fusion, Intelligent Control, Sensor Systems.

INTRODUCTION

In today's conditions of rapid development of high-tech production, digitalization of industry and widespread implementation of smart control systems, research in the field of robotics is becoming particularly relevant, in particular, the development of effective decision-making models for collaborative robot manipulators. Industry 5.0, which is the next stage in the evolution of industrial paradigms, focuses on deep interaction between man and machine, where the robot not only performs programmed actions, but is also able to adapt its behavior to a changing environment, interact with the operator in a shared workspace and make safe and effective decisions in real time [1]-[14].

In this context, the use of collaborative robot manipulators with advanced mechanisms of sensory perception and decision-making is a key element in creating flexible and adaptive cyber-physical production systems. In conditions where not only efficiency, but also safety of cooperation with a person depends on the reliability, accuracy and speed of the robot's response, the task of developing mathematically based models that take into account information from various sources of environmental observation and allow for situation-oriented behavior [15]-[30]. Combining the methods of Sensor Fusion and Rule-based Systems in the control process opens up opportunities for creating intelligent behavior models that combine the accuracy of formal algorithms with the flexibility of logical rules. Sensor Fusion allows for consistent processing of information from several sensors, reducing the impact of noise, increasing the reliability of assessing the state of objects and the environment, while Rule-based Systems provide understandable, controlled and interpreted decision-making, which is especially important in conditions of high requirements for the safety and transparency of robotic systems. Such a combination is relevant and necessary within the framework of Industry 5.0, where automated systems must not only perform tasks, but also be capable of autonomous situation analysis, adaptation to changing context and effective interaction with a person.

The proposed research is aimed at formalizing such a combined decision-making model, its mathematical justification, and practical application in collaborative robotic manipulator control tasks, which is an important step towards the development of intelligent, safe, and human-centric robotic systems. Therefore, different methods and approaches can also be used here [31]-[50].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Kermenov R. studies the automation of the manual stacking process by removing protective film using collaborative robots, demonstrating the potential of such systems in assembly operations [51]. This solution provides increased accuracy and safety of the process, but does not focus on decision-making based on sensor data.

Gao Z. proposes adaptive safety control using an energy reservoir of tasks in a changing environment, which is relevant for adaptive control tasks in collaborative robotics [52]. This approach can be used to ensure dynamic system response, but does not implement clear rule logic based on specific input signals.

Chaabani A. develops a real-time quality control system using artificial intelligence, which emphasizes the effectiveness of combining AI and robotic systems in manufacturing [53]. This can be a useful example of integrating decision-making rules, but the main focus is on computer vision.

Tiwari R.'s publication presents a combination of sensor fusion and reinforcement learning approaches for robot navigation, which confirms the feasibility of combining methods in complex environments [54]. This approach can be used to expand the adaptation functions of the developed model.

Ušinskis V.'s paper investigates the navigation of an autonomous mobile robot based on sensor fusion, which is highly relevant to the research topic, but does not take into account the logic of rule-based behavior [55].

Karalekas G.'s article examines the teaching of AI and ML in secondary education using robotics, which demonstrates the potential of educational approaches, but is not directly technically applicable in the framework of collaborative robot control [56].

Liu W.'s study combines deep learning methods and rule-based approaches for tile detection, which illustrates the effectiveness of combined models for accurate determination of the object state [57]. This approach confirms the effectiveness of combining rules and learning, but is focused on visual tasks.

Saleem Z.'s paper reviews external sensors for human detection in a collaborative robot environment, which allows conclusions to be drawn about effective sensor types for further use in the development of Sensor Fusion models [58].

Kurniawan W.C.'s paper proposes a system for detecting human movements as nonverbal signals for robot interaction, which emphasizes the importance of interpreting sensory data in decision-making [59].

The overall conclusion is that the analysis confirms the high relevance of developing combined control models for collaborative robots. Most studies demonstrate the effectiveness of sensor fusion or rule-based approaches separately, but insufficient attention has been paid to their integration to create reliable decision-making systems.

A DECISION-MAKING MODEL DEVELOPMENT FOR CONTROLLING A COLLABORATIVE ROBOT-MANIPULATOR

Sensor Fusion is the process of combining data from multiple sensor sources to obtain more accurate, reliable, and complete information about the state of an object or environment than is possible with a single sensor. By merging data from different types of sensors (e.g., from a camera, ultrasonic sensor, IMU, etc.), a system can compensate for the shortcomings of individual sensors, reduce the impact of noise, and improve the quality of decisions. Sensor Fusion is widely used in autonomous robots, navigation systems, unmanned vehicles, and collaborative robots to provide accurate perception of the spatial position of objects, speed of movement, and interaction with a person. Rule-based systems are a class of intelligent systems that make decisions based on predefined rules in the form of logical "IF...THEN..." constructs. Such systems are used to formalize expert knowledge and provide transparent, interpretable behavior of automated or robotic devices. In the context of robot control, rule-based systems allow implementing a sequence of actions depending on the state of sensor data or the external environment, ensuring safe and adaptive interaction with the operator or objects. They are especially effective in tasks where predictability of behavior, ease of updating logic and control over decisions are important.

Based on the definitions proposed above, a two-stage model is proposed, which is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Two-stage decision-making model for controlling a collaborative robot manipulator

Let us describe the principle of operation of a two-stage decision-making model for controlling a collaborative robot-manipulator (Fig. 1):

- the first level (Sensor Fusion), combines data from several sensors (camera, ultrasound, IMU, etc.) to obtain a single assessment of the state of the environment;
- the second level (Rule-based Decision Making), makes decisions based on clearly defined rules and information obtained from data fusion.

The mathematical model of machine data fusion (Sensor Fusion) is proposed to be implemented through a weighted average:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i \cdot \mathbf{z}_i(t)}{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i} \quad (1)$$

$\mathbf{z}_i(t)$ – data vector from the i -th sensor at time t ;

w_i – weight (confidence) to the data of the i -th sensor;

$\mathbf{x}(t)$ – estimated vector of the working environment state (position of objects, person, obstacles, etc.).

If noise needs to be taken into account, this can be done using the Kalman filter:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1} + K_t(\mathbf{z}_t - H\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1}) \quad (2)$$

$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t$ – estimated state at a point in time t ;

\mathbf{z}_t – measured state (data vector);

H – observation matrix;

K_t – Kalman matrix (takes into account measurement and forecast uncertainty).

The decision-making rules (Rule-based system) for the mathematical description of the second level is proposed as follows. Let us have a set of rules of the form:

$$\mathbf{if} \text{ condition } \mathbf{then} \text{ action.} \quad (3)$$

Then the decision-making algorithm will be as follows:

$$u(t) = a_j \text{ such, that } \varphi_j(\mathbf{x}(t)) = 1, \quad (4)$$

$\mathbf{x}(t)$ – input state from Sensor Fusion block;

$\varphi_j(\mathbf{x}(t)) \in \{0,1\}$ – Boolean function for executing a rule condition;

$a_j \in A$ – action (command for the manipulator);

$u(t) \in A$ – selected action.

Based on models (1-4), let us develop a two-stage (combined) decision-making model for controlling a collaborative robot-manipulator (Fig. 1). The combined model will have the following form:

– data fusion

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = f_{fusion}(\{\mathbf{z}_i(t)\}_{i=1}^N, \{w_i\}_{i=1}^N), \quad (5)$$

$\mathbf{x}(t)$ – the estimate or merged state of the system at time t , i.e. the result of the function of merging data from all sensors; it can be position, velocity, temperature, or other integrated characteristic of the environment or object;

$f_{fusion}(\cdot)$ – a fusion function that processes multiple sensor measurements and weights to obtain a generalized, more robust state estimate. This could be, for example, a Kalman filter, a Bayesian model, or another algorithmic scheme;

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$\{z_i(t)\}_{i=1}^N$ – a set of measurements from N sensors at time t , where $z_i(t)$ is the value obtained from the i th sensor at the current time. These measurements can be of different nature (temperature, distance, image, etc.);

$\{w_i\}_{i=1}^N$ – a set of weights that reflect the degree of confidence or importance of each sensor in the fusion process. The value of w_i can be determined depending on the accuracy of the sensor, its noise characteristics, or the context of use.

– rules

$$u(t) = R(x(t)) = a_j \text{ where } \varphi_j(x(t)) = 1, \quad (6)$$

$u(t)$ – a control action or output of the system at time t that is generated based on the current state of the system. It can be a command to a robot manipulator, for example: "move forward", "stop", "dodge", etc.;

$R(x(t))$ – a rule or set of rules that determine which action a_j should be performed given a given state $x(t)$. The function $R(\cdot)$ is a logical mechanism for transforming a state into an action based on specified conditions

$x(t)$ – system state or fused sensor data at time t ; may include object position, velocity, recognized features, etc. This is the input to the rule logic;

a_j – a specific action or reaction of the system that is performed when the rule φ_j is true. It is a set of permissible actions, each of which corresponds to a specific scenario or conditions;

$\varphi_j(x(t))$ – a boolean condition (logical rule) that checks whether a certain situation is true for state $x(t)$. If the condition is true ($\varphi_j(x(t)) = 1$), then the corresponding action a_j is activated. For example: "if the distance is less than 30 cm and the speed is greater than 0 – stop".

The developed combined model, which combines the Sensor Fusion and Rule-based Systems methods, has a number of important advantages that make it particularly effective for controlling a collaborative robot-manipulator. Due to the fusion of data from different types of sensors, high accuracy, noise resistance and reliability of environmental assessment are achieved, which is critically important for safe interaction with a person. At the same time, the use of logically formalized rules allows for transparent, controlled and easily modified decision-making, which is well suited for a dynamic production environment. The model guarantees adaptive behavior of the robot in conditions of uncertainty, reduces the risk of collisions, increases the level of process automation and reduces dependence on fully learning algorithms. In addition, such a model is easily scalable, verifiable and can be integrated into existing robotic complex control systems.

Let us give an example of the developed combined model implementation. Let us simulate the following scenario: The robot should stop moving if the operator approaches closer than 0.5 m.

Given: camera $z_1(t)$ = human hand position (x, y, z) and Ultrasonic sensor $z_2(t)$ = distance to operator.

Then data fusion (simplified representation):

$$x(t) = \frac{w_1 \cdot z_1(t) + w_2 \cdot z_2(t)}{w_1 + w_2} \quad (7)$$

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$x(t)$ – weighted average or merged result of the system state assessment at time t , which takes into account the contribution of each sensor according to its reliability;

$z_1(t)$, $z_2(t)$ – values received from the first and second sensors at time t ; these can be measurements of temperature, distance, speed, etc.;

w_1 , w_2 – weighting coefficients reflecting the degree of confidence in each sensor: the higher the accuracy or importance of the sensor, the higher its coefficient w .

Let $w_1=0.7$; $w_2 = 0.3$; $z_1(t) = 0.6$; $z_2(t)=0.4$.

$$x(t) = \frac{0.7 \cdot 0.6 + 0.3 \cdot 0.4}{1.0} = 0.54 \quad (8)$$

Rule:

$$\text{if } x(t) < 0.54 \text{ then stop the robot} \quad (9)$$

So, from (9) we see that $x(t)=0.54$, this means that the condition is not met, i.e. the robot must continue moving.

A PROGRAM FOR MODELING A COMBINED DECISION-MAKING MODEL OPERATION DEVELOPMENT

The choice of the Python programming language is due to its widespread use in robotics, machine learning, and data processing, which provides ease of development, high code readability, and the availability of a large number of libraries for scientific and technical calculations [60]-[64]. Python is supported by a community of researchers and developers of robotic systems, which simplifies integration with hardware, sensor modules, and artificial intelligence algorithms. The matplotlib.pyplot library was chosen because of its ability to create high-quality visualization of results in the form of graphs, which is necessary for analyzing the behavior of the data fusion model and making decisions. It allows you to build interactive graphs, compare values from different sources, and clearly demonstrate the operation of control rules. The combination of Python and matplotlib provides effective development, debugging, and visual testing of a combined model for controlling a collaborative robot-manipulator. Here is an example of the implementations of the modeling program:

```
# Setting artificial data from sensors
time = np.linspace(0, 10, 100) # 100 time points from 0 to 10 seconds
z1 = 40 + 10 * np.sin(time) # Data from sensor 1 (e.g. distance)
z2 = 60 + 15 * np.cos(time) # Data from sensor 2
```

This code snippet is used to simulate artificial data that simulates signals from two sensors in the time domain. It allows you to test the operation of the combined model without the need to connect real equipment, which simplifies the development and visualization of the algorithm.

```
# Sensor weights (confidence)
w1 = 0.6
w2 = 0.4
```

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This code snippet defines weights that reflect the degree of confidence in each sensor when fusing data. A higher weight value means a higher confidence in the reliability of the data from that sensor.

```
# Sensor Fusion
def sensor_fusion(z1, z2, w1, w2):
    return (w1 * z1 + w2 * z2) / (w1 + w2)
```

This fragment implements the function of merging data from two sensors using a weighted average, where each sensor signal is taken into account according to a given confidence (weight). This approach allows you to get a more accurate and reliable assessment of the system state based on heterogeneous information.

```
# Rule-Based System
def rule_based_control(x):
    if x < 30:
        return "Stop"
    elif x < 70:
        return "Slow down"
    else:
        return "Continue moving"
```

This code snippet implements decision logic based on a set of rules that react to the values of the merged data. It allows the system to determine the robot's control action based on the current state of the environment.

```
# Calculating merged values and corresponding decisions
x_fused = sensor_fusion(z1, z2, w1, w2)
actions = [rule_based_control(x) for x in x_fused]
```

Let's simulate the operation of the combined method based on the developed program under the following input conditions: time (sec) - 100 time points from 0 to 10 seconds; z_1 - Data from sensor 1 ($z_1 = 40 + 10 * \text{np.sin}(\text{time})$); z_2 - Data from sensor 2 ($z_2 = 60 + 15 * \text{np.cos}(\text{time})$); $w_1 = 0.6$ - weights of the first sensor; $w_2 = 0.4$ - weights of the second sensor. Rules: If the combined value $< 30 \rightarrow$ action: "Stop"; If $30 \leq \text{value} < 70 \rightarrow$ action: "Slow down"; If $\geq 70 \rightarrow$ action: "Continue moving". The result of the simulation of the combined Sensor Fusion and Rule based methods is shown in Figure 2.

The graph (Fig. 2) shows the result of the combined control model of a collaborative robot-manipulator based on data fusion (Sensor Fusion) and rules (Rule-based System). The lines labeled Sensor 1 (z_1) and Sensor 2 (z_2) display the initial signals from the two sensors, which vary within approximately 30 to 50 units (z_1) and from 45 to 75 units (z_2) during the time interval from 0 to 10 seconds. The green line Data fusion ($x(t)$) is the result of merging these two signals with weights of 0.6 and 0.4, respectively, which allows obtaining a smoothed and consistent assessment of the state of the environment. The values of $x(t)$ vary from approximately 39 to 56 units, without reaching limits below 30 or above 70, which has a direct impact on the action according to the defined rules.

Figure 2: Graph of the results obtained when modeling the combined Sensor Fusion and Rule based methods

According to the logic of the rules, throughout the entire time interval, the fusion result $x(t)$ is in the range from 30 to 70, which means that the action performed by the system is constantly equal to "Slow down". This indicates a stable situation in the robot's workspace, without critical fluctuations that could cause an emergency stop or, conversely, unhindered continuation of movement. This result confirms the effectiveness of the chosen fusion method, since even in the presence of a significant difference between individual sensor measurements (for example, at points where z_1 is about 30 and z_2 is more than 70), the model provides an averaged controlled result. The conclusion is that the combined model allows reducing the influence of noise and inaccuracies of individual sensors, stabilizes control signals and ensures safe behavior of the robot system in accordance with predefined conditions.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the research, a combined decision-making model was developed for controlling a collaborative robot-manipulator, which integrates the method of data fusion (Sensor Fusion) and the system of rules (Rule-Based Systems). This approach allows you to effectively combine information from several sensors, taking into account their weight, which allows you to obtain a more reliable and stable assessment of the state of the environment. The use of rules provides transparent, interpretable and operational decision-making, which is especially important in conditions of interaction with a person and a changing production environment. The simulation showed that the combined model provides stable control of the robotic system without critical fluctuations and reduces the risk of false responses to noisy or unstable signals. Graphical analysis confirmed that the values after fusion remain within the safe operating range, which allows the system to operate in a reduced speed mode, avoiding danger and ensuring smooth operation.

The proposed model scales well to a larger number of sensors and more complex rules, which expands its potential for application in industrial systems of Industry 5.0. For further research, it is

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recommended to integrate machine learning methods for automatic adaptation of weights and rules in real time, which will allow achieving a higher level of autonomy and intelligent control. Also promising is the implementation of fuzzy logic and neural network approaches to rule formation, as well as expanding the sensor set of the system to take into account visual, sound and temperature data.

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